

Multispectral drone imagery as a tool for estimating nitrogen and chlorophyll content in Alfalfa Crops and its co-comparison with field results

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Keywords: Alfalfa Crops, Drones, Multispectral Sensors, SPAD, Spain.

One of Spain's most important forage crops, especially in the Castilla y León region, is the alfalfa cultivation. This leguminous crop requires special attention with regard to its nitrogen and chlorophyll levels, elements that are fundamental to protein synthesis and the photosynthesis process, and which largely determine the plant's development and productivity. The aim of this research is to evaluate the effectiveness of drone remote sensing in estimating nitrogen and chlorophyll levels in Alfalfa crops, and to compare it with traditional measurement methods. The study was carried out on an alfalfa plot in Palencia (Spain), combining three different methodologies: drone remote sensing, SPAD measurements and laboratory analysis. The sampling in the field was carried out at ten random points over four consecutive weeks, analyzing two plants per point and two leaves per plant (upper and lower). Simultaneous drone operations were carried out at each sampling time, generating three vegetation indices using the Pix4D software processing. Furthermore, a laboratory analysis was carried out to determine the percentage of crude protein and nitrogen in the plant, in order to validate the accuracy of the remote measurements. In parallel with this fieldwork, a systematic review of the literature in Web of Science and Scopus was carried out, yielding a total of 55 highly relevant articles, revealing that there is limited specific literature on alfalfa, but a great amount of methodological information. Indeed, the results indicate that the effectiveness of vegetation indices varies according to the phenological phase of the crop. Significant differences were observed between nutrient levels in the upper and lower parts of the plants, with a higher concentration in the upper leaves due to better light exposure and greater absorption capacity. This study is considered a fundamental basis for future scientific studies related to remote sensing estimation of nitrogen and chlorophyll using drones in alfalfa cultivation, and which will help further investigations pursuing this goal.

Acknowledgements (optional):